

IMPROVED LARGE-SCALE JOINT PERFORMANCE USING 3-D WOVEN NON-CRIMP FABRICS

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SUMMARY

The fabrication and performance of large-scale composite T-joints is investigated. Various joints were fabricated using 2-D and 3-D woven fabric reinforced composites to transfer load between the vertical and horizontal members. Joints were tested by applying a pull-off load to the vertical member. The sequence of failure events was studied. Static test results were ranked by energy absorption. Dynamic tests were also conducted and compared to the static results. In both load cases, the joints incorporating 3-D fabrics to join the horizontal and vertical bulkheads provided superior performance.

Keywords: VARTM, Joining, Textiles, 3-D weaving, Composites, Mechanical Testing

FABRICATION AND TEST RESULTS

Composite sandwich elements are commonly used in ship structures. Carbon fiber composites used as face-sheets represent an opportunity to further reduce weight by increasing specific stiffness and strength of the structural elements. Joining methods are needed to assemble composite sandwich elements into ship structures. The typical situation of the sandwich and joint parts would be subjected to out-of-plane loading. The resulting interlaminar stresses require special attention in the joint design to avoid delamination failure modes that are common in 2-D laminates [1-9]. 3-D woven preforms offer at least an order of magnitude increase in interlaminar fracture toughness. This study experimentally investigates the potential of 3-D woven non-crimp carbon preforms to improve joint performance versus a 2-D woven baseline in a T-joint configuration.

In orthogonal 3-D weaves, the through thickness yarns are perpendicular to the plane of the fabric, as shown in Figure 1. The fabric is held together with the Z yarns. Using the multi-rapier process, such as that invented at NC State University [10] and further

developed and commercialized by 3TEX [11, 12], all layers of filling yarns are simultaneously inserted in a single machine cycle. Thus, composites based on such unitary orthogonal non-crimp 3-D woven preforms, manufactured by this process, compare favorably in cost with hand laid 2-D laminates, especially as the number of layers increases.

Figure 1. Schematic of an orthogonal non-crimp 3-D weave and photos of the 3TEX's 3-D weaving machines.

This 3TEX 3-D weaving technology allows for splitting of the preform where a single thick section preform can transition into multiple thinner layers while maintaining their individual Z-reinforcement. This allows for the novel preform constructions where the fabric can be folded in a continuous Π or an H joint configuration. Figure 2 shows an example of a 3TEX preform that has been manufactured to possess regions of multiple 3-D layers that can be positioned to form a Π joint.

Figure 2. Woven flat fabric with flaps that unfold to desired shape, in this case a “ Π ”.

Several 48 inch by 24 inch large bulkheads were fabricated using a quasi-isotropic lay-up to produce an approximately 1/8” thick face sheet of T700 carbon fabric composite. 2 inch and 3 inch thick balsa cores from Baltek (LAMPREP SB100) were used as the core material for the vertical and horizontal bulkhead, respectively. A typical VARTM setup was used to infiltrate the fabric with Ashland Derakane 510-A Vinyl-Ester resin. After cure and debagging, the parts were machined into 3.5 inch wide beams. Eight different large-scale joint configurations were evaluated in this paper; their schematics are shown in Figure 3. Four Joints (A-D) used two 7-inch triangular cores at the intersection between the vertical and horizontal bulkheads and four joints used pre-made carbon composite flanges (E-H).

Figure 3. Schematic of T-joint configuration and 3-D preform with integrated flaps.

A 3/16 inch thick face sheet using 2-D fabric for Joint A and a 3/16 inch thick 3TEX preform for Joint B were placed on the triangular core, extended onto the composite panel and infused under vacuum with the Ashland Derakane 510-A Vinyl-Ester resin. Joint C wrapped two 3TEX flap fabrics around the triangular core with one of the flaps overlapping on the long side of the core and extending onto either bulkhead, while the other flap was positioned under the triangular core ending at the bulkhead corner. Joint D was identical to Joint C with the exception that the thin horizontal bulkhead flap wrapped around the 90° bulkhead corner.

The flange approach used pre-made VARTM infused 2-D (3/16 inch) for Joint E and one layer of 3TEX 3-D fabric (3/16 inch for Joint F and 3/32 inch for Joint G). Joint H used the split preform to allow transition from a thick, single-layer 3-D preform into two thinner, also single-layer 3-D preforms (same as Joints C and D). Figure 4 shows Flanges G and H prior to bonding. All flanges were adhesively bonded to the structure using a Plexus adhesive (AO420).

Figure 4. Flange approach with and without split preform

Figure 5 shows the tension test setup and compares the load-bearing capacity of the tested joints at first failure. Joints C and D with the 3-D overwrapped core show the highest load values, with that for Joint C being about twice greater than the baseline Joint A failure load. The flange approach shows a significant reduction in load-bearing capacity, with exception for Joint H.

	Load at first failure [lbs]	Failure Load compared to Baseline (Joint A) [%]
Joint A	1450	100
Joint B	1500	103
Joint C	3000	207
Joint D	2550	176
Joint E	600	41
Joint F	1300	90
Joint G	700	48
Joint H	1800	124

Figure 5: Test setup and load-bearing capacity of various joint configurations of 3.5 inch width.

For Joint C and D failure starts in the balsa core (Failure 1). The crack widens and starts to separate the 3-D preform/face sheet that wraps around the cracked core. This debonding of the face sheet from the core continues until it reaches the end of the balsa core where the 3-D flaps separate. Unlike the case of the 2-D material which delaminates along the interface with the structural laminate, in joints C and D, the 3-D perform remains bonded to the structural laminate. Damage propagates along the region between the two flaps. Since this region contains Z-fibers, higher loads are required to propagate the damage. Progressive crack propagation was observed as Z-fibers fail sequentially leading to significant increases in energy absorption. At these higher loads, a third failure is observed, where a crack forms at the horizontal/vertical bulkhead intersection (Failure 3, light green circle). This crack propagates, and finally the complete separation of the joint from the horizontal bulkhead occurs (Failure 4).

Figure 6. Schematic of failure modes

The flange approach showed similar failure mode in the bonding region between horizontal bulkhead and flange. The 2-D flange separated catastrophically as a crack opened where the face sheet is joined to the flange and rapidly propagates until complete separation of the flange. In case of the 3-D material, the crack is arrested by the Z-fibers and propagates slowly as load is increased. Overall, Joint H showed a higher failure load compared to the baseline, though lower compared to Joint D, where the triangular core was used with 3-D woven fabric. The surface preparation (cleaning, sanding) is critical for all joints using non-split preforms as the failure of these joints is governed by the strength of the adhesive bond between the bulkhead and joint. The split preform joints fail in the split region and thus a good surface preparation is not as critical compared to the other joint approaches making this approach more tolerant to any process variation.

Figure 7. Catastrophic failure seen in Joints E, F, G (left) versus progressive failure in split flange.

Energy absorption was calculated for the static tests to rank joint performance during dynamic loading (see Figure 8). Here, the energy levels were taken by integrating the load-deflection curves until peak load levels were reached. In general, the flange approach does not work as well as the triangular core approach, except for the 3TEX flap flange approach. Joints C and D with the 3TEX flap showed a significant increase (approximately 150%-200%) in the energy absorption as compared to the baseline joint. The increase in energy levels is due to the higher static load-bearing capacity of the joints and their ability to endure the load even after first failure. The flange approach with flaps showed a 250% increase in energy absorption levels compared to the baseline. The reduced stiffness of the joint, in conjunction with fairly high load levels at failure, allowed for a high energy absorption of this joining concept. The flange approach merits consideration as it significantly reduces weight compared to the core insert approach.

Figure 8. Load and energy capacity of various joint configurations.

In addition to the static mechanical tests, shock tests were performed based on MIL-S 901 D. Three specimens were down-selected from the static tests; those included the baseline joint (Joint A), 3TEX triangular core joint (Joint D) and 3TEX flange joint (Joint H). Two parameters can be changed during testing. Additional weights can be added to the vertical bulkhead and the height of the impact hammer can be varied increasing the acceleration level. A high-speed video was used to visualize any major

defect or crack development and an accelerometer placed on the vertical bulkhead weights was used to calculate the approximate load level of the joint. An example of raw and band-pass filtered acceleration for a hammer blow for Joint A is provided below. A positive acceleration is seen initially, when the table is hit by the impact hammer accelerating the horizontal bulkhead upwards and putting the joint under compression. After 2 inches the table stop is hit, and the horizontal bulkhead moves downward putting the joint under tension. Maximum tension load can be approximated by the load added to the vertical bulkhead multiplied by the maximum negative acceleration ($m \cdot a$).

Figure 9. Typical acceleration data during shock testing.

The test was started with the baseline Joint A. In total, 6 blows (hammer impacts) were conducted. Blows 1-3 used 3, 6 and 12 inch hammer heights and a total of 64 lb weights attached to the vertical bulkhead. Blows 4-6 added hammer heights at 6, 12 and 24 inches with a total weight of 140 lbs. After Blow 3 some cracks developed on one side of the core, but the crack length did not increase in Blows 4 and 5. Blow 6 resulted in catastrophic failure of the joint with separation of the horizontal bulkhead from the joint (see Figure 10). The high-speed video suggests that the crack opened and propagated rapidly (less than 1 frame or 1/250s) until full failure of the joint. The maximum acceleration measured was approximately 71g during Blow 6.

Figure 10. High-speed camera detects failure of triangular core during Joint A testing.

Joint D with split 3TEX preform and overwrapped balsa core was also tested. Joint D had 6 blows at 3, 6, 12, 18, 24, 30 and 36 inches height and 140 lbs weight. During the fourth blow the balsa core failed close to load nose in shear (blue circle in Figure 11). Visually, the joint stayed perfectly intact and survived the maximum load and an acceleration of 106 g applied during the 36 inch hammer drop.

Figure 11. High-speed camera detects failure of sandwich core during Joint D testing.

Finally, 3TEX flange Joint H was tested. Joint H was evaluated with 5 blows at 3, 6, 12, 18, and 24 inches height and 140 lbs weights and the weights attached near the vertical bulkhead top. Two 2-inch square tubes were welded in parallel of the vertical bulkhead to ensure the reduced movement perpendicular to the impact direction. Reducing rocking motion was seen during initial tests. During Blow 5 the horizontal bulkhead failed without damage in the joint, as seen in Figure 12. A maximum acceleration of 72 g was measured.

Figure 12. Test setup and large crack development in the sandwich core after Blow 5.

Figure 13 summarizes the static and shock test results. Here, the load capacity is normalized by the width of the specimen as static (3.5 inches) and shock (20 inches) specimen width varied. Both shock and static failure loads are comparable. The baseline joint showed the lowest load bearing capacity of the joints tested for both static and dynamic testing conditions. The 3TEX balsa core insert approach (Joint D)

showed a significant increase in static test load capacity. Also, the Joint D shock loading was the highest, ultimate load capacity is most likely higher as the specimens failed in the horizontal bulkhead (i.e. the interface region of the joint did not fail in the same mode as in the static test).

The novel joint design with Flange (Joint H) shows similar but slightly higher static and dynamic load capacity while reducing weight and improving manufacturability. On the other hand, Joint D requires similar installation procedures compared to the baseline, but shows a significant increase in both static and dynamic load bearing capacity.

Figure 13. Comparison of static and dynamic test results.

CONCLUSIONS

3-D orthogonal non-crimp woven fabrics and novel joining concepts based on these fabrics have been evaluated for large-scale joints. Eight joining concepts have been realized by fabricating experimental joint samples, which were then tested statically. Three additional joints were fabricated and tested dynamically. This study showed the clear benefits of 3-D woven non-crimp fabrics. In particular, the split preform allows for a crack arresting at the split and ultimately increasing joint performance by more than 100%. Both the radically improved interlaminar fracture properties of the materials and unique dimensional configurations of the joints developed here can be further used to optimize large-scale composite joint designs.

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References

1. J. W. Gillespe, Jr, A. Obst, R. C. Don, K. T. Kedward and J. Bish, "Joint Design for Marine Structures", NSWC Carderock Final Report, 1997.
2. Guenon, V. A., J. W. Gillespie Jr., and T-W. Chou, "A Modified Double Cantilever Beam Specimen for Testing the Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Three Dimensional Composites," Proceedings of the Fabricating Composites '87 Conference, Society of Manufacturing Engineers, Philadelphia, PA, 1987.
3. Guenon, V., T-W. Chou, and J. W. Gillespie Jr., "Toughness Properties of a Three Dimensional Carbon/Epoxy Composite," Journal of Materials Science, Vol. 24, No. 11, pp. 4168–4175, November 1989.
4. Byun, J. H., J. W. Gillespie Jr., and T-W. Chou, "Mode I Delamination of a Three-Dimensional Fabric Composite," Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 24, No. 5, pp. 497–518, May 1990.
5. Byun, J. H., T. W. Chou, and J. W. Gillespie Jr., "Mode II Delamination of Three-Dimensional Textile Structural Composites," Proceedings of the American Society for Composites Fourth Technical Conference, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc., Inc., Lancaster, PA, 1989.
6. H. J. Phillips and R. A. Sheno, "Damage tolerance of laminated tee joints in FRP structures," Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, vol. 29, pp. 465-478, 1998.
7. R. A. Sheno and G. L. Hawkins, "Influence of material and geometry variations on the behaviour of bonded tee connections in FRP ships," Composites, vol. 23, pp. 335-345, 1992.
8. A. R. Dodkins, R. A. Sheno, and G. L. Hawkins, "Design of joints and attachments in FRP ships' structures," Marine Structures, vol. 7, pp. 365-398, 1994.
9. A. R. Rispler, G. P. Steven, and L. Tong, "Failure Analysis of Composite T-Joints Including Inserts," Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, vol. 16, pp. 1642-1658, 1997.
10. M.H. Mohamed and Z. Zhang, "Method of forming variable cross-sectional shaped three-dimensional fabrics", U.S. Patent 5,085,252 (February 4, 1992), to North Carolina State University.
11. Mohamed, M.H., Bogdanovich, A.E., Dickinson, L.C., Singletary, J.N., Lienhart, R.B., "A new generation of 3D woven fabric preforms an composites", SAMPE Journal, 37(3), pp. 8-17, 2001.
12. Mohamed, M.H., Bogdanovich, A.E., "Comparative analysis of different 3D weaving processes, machines and products", Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-17), 2009, Edinburgh, UK.